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Modelling of multi-energy systems of residential buildings with Calliope and validation of results

U Schilt^{1,2*}, E Linder¹, M Meyer¹, S Schneeberger¹, A Melillo¹, P Roos³,
P Schuetz¹

¹ Competence Centre for Thermal Energy Storage, School of Engineering and Architecture, Lucerne University of Applied Sciences, Horw, Switzerland

² School of Architecture, Civil and Environmental Engineering, École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne (EPFL), Lausanne, Switzerland

³ Cowa Thermal Solutions AG, Lucerne, Switzerland

* Corresponding author: ueli.schilt@hslu.ch

Abstract. Given the current and future importance of energy availability in the residential sector, there is great interest in reducing and optimising the energy consumption of single and multi-family houses. An energy system consisting of solar PV, heat pump, and battery and thermal storage can reduce electricity grid dependence by maximising the use of renewable energy. However, creating a model for such a multi-energy system can be challenging due to the need for detailed input data and high computational cost. This study aimed to develop a simpler model with short computation times and sufficient accuracy by employing a mixed-integer linear programming (MILP) method based on the modelling framework Calliope, allowing the investigation of optimal operation regarding energy consumption and autarky. The results of a model simulation were compared to measurements acquired at a pilot site of a residential building in an alpine region of Switzerland. The results show good agreement between the model and pilot site for PV self-consumption (-5%), grid-export (+3%), and battery usage (-2%), whereas larger discrepancies were observed for the utilisation of the thermal storage (-78%). With the necessary modifications the developed model will be useful in estimating the feasibility and impact of multi-energy systems in residential buildings.

1. Introduction

The deployment of an energy system consisting of solar photovoltaics (PV), heat pump, and battery and thermal energy storage (TES) in residential buildings is an effective approach for reducing energy consumption from the grid, while decreasing the carbon footprint by maximising the use of renewable energy [1]. A model of the system can be deployed to estimate the energy consumption and generation, the required size of the equipment, as well as to identify control challenges. Complex models based on a detailed physical description of the system have shown to yield accurate results [2]. However, these models require a very detailed model input which is often not available. Furthermore, complex models come at a high computational cost if optimisation is to be performed, as mentioned in Gabrielli et al. [3]. The development of a simpler model for fast computing with sufficient accuracy is the aim of this work. Such a model could be useful for first estimations of system feasibility, as well as for equipment sizing, supporting the control strategy, or for integration into a larger simulation model. Importantly, if

the model can be integrated in a linear programming framework, optimum system performance along different target functions such as energy efficiency and autarky can be investigated.

We present a multi-energy system model based on the modelling framework Calliope [4]. The framework relies on a mixed-integer linear programming (MILP) method, thereby resulting in shorter computation times compared to non-linear optimisation methods. Several studies of multi-energy systems of various sizes have been carried out using Calliope. While Calliope has mostly been used for the modelling of energy systems on district, national, and multi-national scale, the model developed in this study describes the energy system of a residential building consisting of solar PV, heat pump, battery storage, and TES. The results of a simulation carried out over several weeks of operation are compared to measurements acquired at a pilot site from a residential building in an alpine region of Switzerland. While the model shows good agreement with the measured data for metrics such as PV self-consumption, grid-export, and battery usage, there is a difference between model results and the real-world system in the way the TES is used. Reasons for this difference are discussed and possible improvements to the model are proposed.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Pilot site – layout, control, and data acquisition

Pilot-site measurement data for validation of the model was obtained from a residential multi-energy system located in the alpine village of Pany, Switzerland. The pilot installation is part of a system validation campaign carried out by Cowa Thermal Solutions AG, a startup company providing thermal energy storage solutions using phase change materials. Detailed information about the system setup, data acquisition, as well as the measurement campaign can be found in the provided research report [5].

The multi-energy system provides heat and electricity to a single-family house (SFH). The roof of the building is equipped with a 17kW_p solar PV system with orientation towards east and west. Additional electricity is provided via grid connection. A 7.7kWh electric battery stores excess PV power and can also be used for islanding operation. Heat is provided via a 14kW_{th} heat pump, which is used for space heating, as well as for the provision of domestic hot water (DHW). A TES buffer tank (760l) is connected to the heat pump, which is used for space heating. A separate storage tank is used for DHW. In both storage units (TES and DHW), additional heat can be provided to the storage via electric resistance heaters that are inserted into the tanks. The system is operated using a hierarchical control strategy with predefined prioritisations. The total electricity demand is a combination of household demand and heat pump demand. Generated solar PV power is used to supply the electricity demand. If there is not enough PV power available, additional electric power is imported from the grid. If there is excess PV power available, the electric battery is being charged. If the electric battery is fully charged and there is still excess PV power available, it is used to charge the thermal storage tanks. This is either done via heat pump (if excess PV power $> 2\text{kW}$), or via the electric resistance heaters (if excess PV power $< 2\text{kW}$). In either scenario, the DHW tank is prioritised over the TES tank.

The electricity generation and consumption of the system is monitored using data from a smart meter and from the PV inverter. The charging and discharging of the battery is also recorded. To calculate the heat flow balances, the inlet- and outlet temperatures of each stream, and the flow rates are recorded. Additionally, five temperature sensors at different heights are placed inside the TES tank to monitor the state-of-charge. The data acquisition system is described in more detail in the pilot site research report [5]. The raw data is available in 5-minute timesteps. For the analysis of the system, the measurement data was aggregated into hourly data so that it can be compared to the model, which is simulated using hourly timesteps. An energy balance for each component, as well as the load was carried out on an hourly basis.

2.2. Calliope energy systems optimisation modelling framework

The model presented in this work was created using Calliope, a MILP energy systems optimisation modelling framework. Calliope uses linear equations for the modelling of energy conversion, transport, transmission, and storage. It allows for the modelling and optimisation of large-scale multi-energy systems such as districts, cities, countries, or continents. Calliope itself is based on the optimisation framework Pyomo in Python programming language. Optimisation is carried out based on a single- or multi-objective cost-optimisation function. It can either be a monetary cost or an otherwise defined cost (e.g. CO₂ intensity). For this study, single-objective optimisation was applied and the ‘cbc’ solver was used.

2.3. Residential multi-energy system model

Figure 1. Layout of the multi-energy system (MES) model, a simplified representation of the MES pilot-site.

The model presented in this work is a representation of the multi-energy system described in Section 2.1. The model includes a PV system, grid connection, heat pump, TES for space heating, battery storage, and a thermal and electric load. For simplicity and due to the fact that the focus of this study was on the TES for space heating, the DHW buffer tank was not modelled separately. Instead, it was lumped together with the thermal load for space heating, whereby the measured heat delivered to the DHW tank was added to the total thermal load profile.

Further, the resistance heaters were also not modelled separately, but lumped together with the heat pump model. This is justified as the contribution of resistance heaters is marginally small (1%). Losses have not been introduced in the model. A schematic representation of the model is shown in Figure 1. In the following, a description of every model component is given.

Instead of modelling the PV system as a technology, the solar PV power profile is taken from the measured data of the pilot site. The measured PV yield is passed as time-series to the model. In the model, the full PV yield is forced, i.e., a power down-regulation by the PV inverter is not allowed. The grid connection is modelled as an electricity source that can be used whenever there is a shortcoming of electricity to meet the demand profile. The capacity of the grid supply was chosen to be very large so that there is no unmet demand. The heat pump is modelled as a conversion technology with electricity as an input and heat as an output. The coefficient of performance (COP) is assumed to be constant, resulting in the following conversion equation:

$$P_{th, hp} = COP * P_{el, hp} \tag{1}$$

$P_{th, hp}$ is the thermal output (kW) and $P_{el, hp}$ is the electric input (kW). Even though in reality the heat pump has a minimum thermal power of 5.7kW_{th}, a continuous operation starting from 0kW is allowed in the model. Otherwise, an additional integer variable would have to be introduced in the model, increasing computation time during optimisation. Taking into account the maximum thermal capacity $P_{th, hp, max}$ of the heat pump, this results in the following inequality constraint:

$$0kW \leq P_{th, hp} \leq P_{th, hp, max} \tag{2}$$

The thermal and the electric storage are modelled as a simple energy balance, i.e., by adding and subtracting the incoming and outgoing energy flows from the previous storage state, respectively.

Temperatures are therefore not considered in the model. Due to the relatively high cycling frequencies observed in the measurement data, storage losses are not considered. Furthermore, losses are omitted to quantify the effect of this simplification. Skipping losses reduces the number of required parameters. Eventually, storage losses would result in a prioritisation of one storage system during the optimisation process due to its storage efficiency, which in turn relies on the chosen values for the loss parameters. However, as a first approach, the selection of the two storage systems should be performed agnostic to its efficiency. Based on the monitoring data from the battery storage, the battery is only discharged down to a minimum state-of-charge of 19%. In the model, this is considered by reducing the battery capacity accordingly. From the measurement data, it was further observed that the TES was operated at temperatures up to 60°C at the top node and that heat was extracted at about 35°C. As a result, the actual capacity of the store was chosen to be 17kWh in the model. The load profiles for heat and electricity are taken from the measured data. The heat load profile combines the demand for space heating and DHW. The electricity load profile only considers the “household demand”, as the power demand of the heat pump depends on the heat pump operation, which is a decision variable of the optimisation. Therefore, the total electricity consumption at a specific timestep can differ between measured and simulated data.

2.4. Optimisation and objective function

In this study, the system is optimised for operation only as the component sizes are already given by the pilot system. The chosen objective is “minimisation of monetary system operation cost”:

$$\min_{c_i} C_{sys} = \min \sum_{t=1}^N (c_{grid} E_{grid} + c_{PV} E_{PV} + c_{battery} E_{battery} + c_{HP} Q_{HP} + c_{TES} Q_{TES})_t \quad (3)$$

To calculate an overall system operation cost C_{sys} , a specific operation cost c_i (e.g. in CHF/kWh) is allocated to each technology i . The specific cost is then multiplied with the Electricity E or heat Q provided by the respective technology for each timestep t and summed up across all timesteps N . In the context of this study, the absolute cost values are not significant; only the relative cost of one technology to the others is relevant. This scaling defines a hierarchy of priority among the different technologies. It is assumed that there is no remuneration for feed-in to the electricity grid. In this study, only the cost for grid-electricity was set to a value larger than zero, whereas all other costs were set to zero.

3. Results

To investigate the validity of our multi-energy system model, we worked with pilot-site measurement data that was recorded during the heating season of 2021/2022, where data from 19.11.2021 until 31.05.2022 was evaluated. The period between 5.2.-13.3.2022 was excluded due to a monitoring system outage. The simulation included an optimisation of system operation. The execution time of the

Figure 2. Comparison of cumulative energy balance of measured and modelled system for the periods from 19.11.2021 to 04.02.2022 and 14.03.2022 to 31.05.2022. Model results are labelled with the percentage agreement with the measured data.

Figure 3. Cumulative charging of thermal energy storage (TES) and battery storage for the period from 14.03.2022 to 31.05.2022. Graph shows values from pilot-site (“measured”) and results from simulation (“model”).

simulation was also measured, as one of the objectives of this study was to achieve short computation times. The runtime for an hourly simulation comprising the whole heating period (19.11.2021-31.05.2022) took 21 seconds computation time on an Intel Core i7-8665U CPU 1.90Ghz, 16.0GB machine.

Figure 4. Hourly energy balance for electricity and heat over 24 hours on 05.04.2022.

the simulation, as well as the pilot-site system prioritise battery storage over thermal storage. This means that excess PV power is used first to charge the battery before charging the TES in case the battery is fully charged. In the case of the pilot-site, this is due to the priority-based control algorithm, whereas in the simulation, it is a decision made by the optimiser.

To investigate the differing behaviour between the simulation model and pilot-site system, we investigated hourly energy balances for heat and electricity. Figure 4 shows the hourly energy balances over 24 hours on 5 April 2022, which was a day with low household-electricity demand, high PV-yield, and average heat demand. One observed difference is the point in time at which the battery is being charged: the actual system charged the battery as soon as the excess PV power was available (at the beginning of the PV-yield cycle), whereas in the model the battery charging was shifted towards the end of the PV-yield cycle. When considering the hourly energy profiles for heat, it becomes apparent that there is a fundamental difference between the model and real-life system in terms of how the TES is operated. While the pilot system charged and/or discharged the TES at every hour, the simulation model only utilised the TES at specific hours - either charging or discharging the system.

4. Discussion and conclusions

The resulting discrepancies between the model results and pilot site measurements can provide valuable insights into the relevant operation parameters of a multi-energy system. We identified several potential reasons that could add to the mentioned discrepancies between the simulation model and pilot system. Firstly, an optimiser is applied to the simulation model, meaning that the simulation has “foresight” of the future system evolution and can therefore time the deployment of technologies accordingly. An example is the charging of the battery, where we observed that in the simulation model the battery was charged at the end of a PV-yield cycle (late afternoon), whereas at the pilot system, it was charged as soon as excess PV power was available. The pilot system does not have such an insight and will try to ensure best use of excess PV power by charging the battery whenever excess power is available. Other

factors include more technical aspects of the system: in the simulation model, the heat pump can run at any continuous capacity, only being restricted by its maximum capacity. In reality, the heat pump must run at a minimum thermal capacity when switched on. If the heat demand is lower than the minimum heat pump capacity, excess heat is generated that will be diverted to the TES. In the same manner, the heat pump at the pilot system has a minimum runtime once switched on, which could again be a source of excess heat being diverted to the TES. Even though the model (due to hourly timesteps) always assumes a heat pump runtime of one hour, the thermal output during one timestep can continuously be regulated since there is no lower boundary for the capacity. Another possible source of the discrepancy could be the selection of the timestep resolution: the controller of the pilot system runs on a higher resolution than one hour, meaning that during the one hour, multiple decision-changes can be implemented, e.g., resulting in charging and discharging of the TES within the same timestep. In contrast, the simulation model only considers one energy balance per timestep. In addition to above-mentioned potential reasons for the discrepancies between model and pilot system, there is also the fact that no losses have been implemented in the simulation model (for the reasons mentioned in Section 2.4.4.). This means that the efficiency and performance of the system are over-estimated by the simulation model. Especially, the use of battery and thermal energy storage introduces charging-, discharging-, and storage-losses, which in reality reduces the overall efficiency of the system and thus increases the overall energy demand.

Overall, the developed model, when modified accordingly, could be useful for estimating the feasibility and impact of multi-energy systems in residential buildings and identify energy savings potentials through optimisation. The knowledge gained in this work can be used to improve both the model, as well as the operation strategy of the real system. The model can be improved in the areas of system control, storage losses, heat pump modelling, and timestep resolution. The real system on the other hand, can potentially improve performance by applying a different control strategy. Due to short computation times, the model could be employed for a model predictive control (MPC) strategy applied to the multi-energy system, taking into account weather forecast and energy demand dynamics in order to reduce the energy consumption.

Future work could include the extension of the existing model into a larger multi-energy system, including several buildings and additional technologies for the modelling of district-size energy hubs.

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